

SmartCorners

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Report on SmartCorners technologies and user-centric vehicle control functionalities.

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1 Executive Summary

The SmartCorners project will mark a turning point in Electric Vehicles (EVs), leveraging the mature technology of In-Wheel Motors (IWMs) adapted for user-centric design. These motors, integrated into multifunctional modules with the powertrain, friction brake, and suspension/steering actuation, offer a compact solution that will enhance various vehicle functionalities. This integration unlocks a wide range of possibilities, redefining EV design and operation. With the adoption of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, SmartCorners will develop and implement an adaptive multilayer control strategy. By analysing historical and real-time data from vehicles, environments, and users – including relevant EV fleets – the project will drive a new idea of software-defined vehicles. This innovative approach will enable rightsizing, holistic optimization, new-generation fault reduction strategies, and personalized system operation, driving efficiency and adaptability to new levels.

The SmartCorners project will have a broad impact, influencing various areas:

1. **Advanced vehicle design**, with innovative skateboard-like chassis configurations.
2. **Energy management**, including pre-conditioning and predictive thermal management while driving.
3. **Comfort and functional aspects**, in terms of user-centric cabin thermal management, and pre-emptive vehicle body control, such as Torque Vectoring Control (TVC) and Active Suspension Systems (ASS).
4. **Recycling process of the vehicle**, reducing waste and impact on climate change.

The simulations, design, and validation methodologies will accelerate the development and industrialization of the project outcomes. This will effectively reduce development time and cost while supporting the adoption of AI-based solutions.

A preliminary discussion with the consortium on different vehicles categories and segments brought the decision to implement the SmartCorners Hardware (HW) and Software (SW) components on **Sport Utility Vehicles (SUVs)**, thanks to their more suitable configuration for SmartCorners System (SCS), as they have high costs and high performances. High-fidelity B-segment EV models will also be considered for simulation testing. In conclusion, SCS will not only provide a significant competitive advantage to the European industry but also contribute to achieving key strategic orientations C and A outlined in the EU Strategic Plan.

The report structure is organized as follows.

Section 2 introduces a high-level overview on vehicle components, innovative control strategies and the EVs available for testing. In Section 3, the main stakeholder groups are listed, specifying their respective roles and interests. Section 4 outlines the systemic approach that will be followed along the project development to achieve the sustainable mobility goals. In Section 5, the main vehicle components are outlined, including the innovative skateboard platform and the SCS components, such as IWMs and active suspension arms and actuators. In Sections 6 and 7, an overview on the state-of-the-art of Energy Efficient Torque Vectoring Control (EETVC) is provided, alongside with innovative AI-based and user-centric control algorithms that the SmartCorners project will bring. Section 8 lists the technical impact categories, e.g. safety, comfort, and efficiency. Section 9 is concluding the deliverable.

2 Introduction

EVs offer different possibilities and configurations, among which the one considered in the SmartCorners project. A new approach, utilizing a skateboard-like flat vehicle chassis, so-called “skateboard platform” (Figure 1a), and SCS (Figure 1b), integrates traction, steering, and suspension functions, boosting performance, safety, and comfort while simplifying vehicle design and repair, maintenance and recycling processes. Some of the advantages of the SCS and the skateboard layout are the assembly time and the free space. Thanks to this compact design, less components and complex assembly operations are needed, hence the interior space for passengers and luggage is increased by 15% and by 20% respectively.

Figure 1: (a) Skateboard platform [1] (b) Smart corner configuration [2]

The SmartCorners project aims to enhance EVs through innovative technologies including IWMs, brake-by-wire systems, and AI-based controls, improving handling and comfort. Adopting a user-centric approach, it follows a V-model development method to ensure breakthrough advancements in vehicle safety, comfort, and efficiency, including the optimization of suspension architecture for reduced size, minimizing linkages, and integrating Active Shock Absorbers (ASA). Using Fiber Reinforced Polymeric (FRP) composites in suspension parts, enhanced with conductive particles for self-sensing capabilities, offers potential for light weighting and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). Self-sensing materials combined with acquisition systems and AI algorithms enable real-time damage detection and load assessment, enhancing vehicle safety and performance.

The addition of IWMs for propulsion increases the unsprung mass, affecting vehicle ride quality and handling. To deal with it, the adoption of ASA (particularly the electromagnetic ones) offers benefits like regenerative capabilities, wide enough actuation bandwidth, and high efficiency. Then, advanced control strategies will optimize comfort and road holding. Adding a composite lever mechanism with self-sensing properties and AI-driven monitoring to rotary electromechanical actuators will further improve performance and reliability.

SmartCorners will employ advanced control strategies enhanced by AI and Digital Twins (DTs), to optimize system operation. Starting from the already well-known Model Predictive Control (MPC) [3] and Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) [4], more innovative control algorithms based on AI will be implemented, such as Neural Network-based Model Predictive Control (NNMPC) [5] and Imitation Learning (IL) [6] leveraging Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) trained through Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). These control strategies will address safety, comfort, and Energy Efficiency (EE) enhancing vehicle dynamics and reducing energy consumption.

Utilizing AVL's toolchain, SmartCorners will develop a high-fidelity model with HW components and SW control algorithms, for testing in simulation. AVL Model.CONNECT tool links simulation models for suspension, active components, proactive control, and thermal management. This

approach ensures effectiveness in execution time, reliability, safety, and cost. Multiple EV demonstrators (Figure 2) will allow an early evaluation of the SmartCorners outcomes, demonstrating vehicle dynamics functions and thermal management aspects, facilitating smooth collaboration.

Figure 2: (a) ELAPHE vehicle platform to test AI based Proactive control strategies; (b) skateboard for chassis dyno tests; (c) AVL vehicle demonstrator for thermal system testing; (d) TUIL demonstrator from EVC1000 for torque-vectoring and active suspension.

2.1 Objectives and Key Performance Improvements of the SCS

The objectives of the SmartCorners project are the following:

1. **Design methodologies (O1):** during the design phase of a vehicle, are considered e.g. efficiency, cost, weight, and space of the powertrain. Considering the complexity of the problem, many researchers propose multi-objective optimisation strategies. To reduce the computational effort of the optimization process model reduction techniques are recommended to simplify the simulation. In this respect, the SCS ambition is to embed fast-running scalable DTs of the SCS in a multi-objective optimization framework that will consider the impact of self-adjusting control strategies during operation and the energy and thermal management of the entire vehicle. Another ambition regarding this topic, is to have the networking of several Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) platform or component test benches to carry out real-time experiment.
2. **SCS design solutions (O2):** on the market are available some innovative corner solutions proposed by industry and academia, so the ambition of the SCS is to achieve so far unexplored levels of flexibility (SCS will be able to embed a different actuator and component sizes for a wide range of EV segments), performance (through regenerative suspension actuators), suspension kinematics control capabilities (toe, camber, and track width control) and practical functionalities for everyday use (e.g. steering-on-the-spot and crab-walking).
3. **Controllers for smart corner operation (O3):** SmartCorners aims to design and incorporate specialized virtual sensors that utilize corner data to take into account both energy consumption and vehicle dynamics. This is possible considering the interrelationships between each corner's behaviour, virtual sensor data, cloud data to generate context and enable proactive control.
4. **Holistic thermal and passenger comfort management (O4):** to consider all the thermal contributions, a holistic and predictive thermal management system with enhanced adaption to environmental conditions is envisaged. The system includes pre-conditioning functions for the main powertrain components and the cabin to balance the trade-off between user experience and energy consumption in different climates.

The main SmartCorners target are reported in Table 1:

Table 1: Main project outputs and relevant type of innovation actions.

Project output	Actions
Asset 1 “Wheel Corner Design”	
PO – 01 Wheel Corner with IWM and integrated chassis actuators.	Simulation, design, preliminary validation, unit testing.
PO – 02 Novel integrated powertrain and chassis controller.	Controller customisation and testing for the specific SCS topology.
PO – 03 SW with adaptable RT AI module for wheel positioning control.	Simulation, Control SW development, Unit testing, Bench testing.
Asset 2 “User-centred Thermal and Cabin Comfort Management”	
PO – 04 AI preconditioning of the thermal system control.	AVL will set up a learning algorithm that detects if a user is about to use the car. AVL DE will use the information to precondition the TS.
PO – 05 Adaptive use of recirculation flap	It will be adapted to the ambient conditions and the number of passengers to demisting and save heating power at the same time.
PO – 06 AI adaption of the comfort settings to user preferences.	Simulation of an adaption and calibration towards a specific user preference.
Asset 3 “Global EV Motion Control”	
PO – 07 Slip control with dynamic tuning and vehicle speed estimator.	Development of AI speed estimator based on ELAPHE vehicle data. Interface for vehicle and environment context-driven dynamic adjustment of control parameters
PO – 08 Pitch, roll and yaw control as a part of a simultaneous 6 DoF control.	Determining comfort behaviour objectives. Development of a vehicle pitch, roll and yaw controllers with IWMs. Model-in-the-loop (MiL), HiL & vehicle validation including validated physics model.
PO – 09 Secondary mode damping control as a part of simultaneous 6DoF control.	Development of secondary damping control with external input interface for road profile (e.g., camera or cloud data). Test with MiL, HiL and on vehicle.
Asset 4 “Smart EV Optimal Operation Management”	
PO – 10 Virtual sensors, including road grip, wheel acceleration and suspension travel.	Modelling virtual sensors with AI approaches. Gathering data with existing vehicle for the training of virtual sensors. Virtual sensing validation via MiL, HiL and on the vehicle.

PO – 11 AI path planning.	Concept development, model building, power management control.
Asset 5 “DT Methodology of User-centred EV design”	
PO – 12 Digital twinning of EV with independent corners.	Implementation, validation and use for design and control.
PO – 13 DTs for AI training.	Build up digital twin model for AI training. AVL DE will do the modelling and AVL will set up the development environment.

To give a quantitative idea of the objectives, the Key Performance Improvements (KPIs) of the project are reported in Table 2:

Table 2: KPIs and objectives of SmartCorners project.

Topics	KPI and SCS contribution
Accelerated design methodologies for component rightsizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >30% reduction of the EV systems development time through the reduction of number of sensors and thanks to the digital twinning of the SCS components (O1, PO-12). • >50% reduction of the calibration parameter (O4, PO-02). • 40% reduction of the number of operations in the control module (O3, PO-07, PO-08).
Increased performance and novel user-centric design and control solutions enabled by AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of the cabin volume by >15% and luggage space by >20% using the skateboard platform (O2, PO-01). • Reduction of vehicle weight by >5% and SCS cost by >15% (O2, PO-01). • 25% reduction of the mass of the suspension components (Section 5.2 and 5.3, O2, PO-01). • 5-to-10% reduction of EV cost (O2, PO-01). • >20% reduction of tyre loads estimation error (O2, PO-03). • 9% increase of the braking energy recovery through control only (O1, PO-02). • 5-10% stopping distance reduction in braking on wet roads (O1, PO-07, PO-10). • >20% autonomy range improvement in real worlds driving conditions (O3, PO-09, PO-11). • 95% of success rate in predictive health monitoring and diagnostics in composite materials components (O3, PO-12, PO-13).
Holistic and integrated thermal management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >25% reduction of the requirement of heating power at 0°C thanks to localised heating surfaces to provide the expected thermal comfort with reduced consumption (Section 7, O4, PO-04, PO-05, PO-06).

3 Identified Stakeholder Groups

The mission of SmartCorners, as depicted in Figure 3, is to strengthen the European innovation ecosystem and value chain by accelerating the uptake of affordable, sustainable, and user centred e-mobility. This will be achieved by a) reducing development time, b) enabling disruptive vehicle architectures based on skateboard layouts, and c) increasing overall EE in real-world operation by developing smart e-corner solutions and AI-based powertrain and chassis control. Evidently, interactions with different stakeholder groups are expected along the project lifetime, to i) fit the technology development to the different users' needs (e.g., vehicle segments, geographical regions), ii) ensure alignment with relevant standards and regulations (existing and oncoming), and iii) properly interface with the relevant actors of the supply chain to ensure industrialisation and uptake of the designed solutions.

Figure 3: SmartCorners at-a-glance.

Already at the stage of defining the SmartCorners project proposal, the following stakeholder groups have been identified:

- 1. End Users:** demand of private and business users for affordable and reliable EVs, well integrated into mobility platforms for additional services. The SCS leads to “better” EV technologies for the end user (e.g. reduced costs, increased performance, safety).
- 2. Automotive Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs):** increasing market share of efficient EVs with a high level of customer acceptance and a high economic and reputation value for the company. SmartCorners intends to address both traditional OEMs and emerging OEMs with high agility to address highly customised solutions. The impact will be created by illustrating technological advances and capabilities to tailor the respective OEM’s portfolio to create revenue through product selling or engineering services.
- 3. Suppliers/engineering:** there is demand on rapid creation of innovations in EV systems and components as well as related technologies, engineering services and data-driven services

for road e-mobility. The impact is created by illustrating technological advances and the capability to transfer Intellectual Property (IP) and/or competencies for revenue creation.

- 4. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs):** increasing positions as a more agile and latitudinous driver of innovations in emerging EV components and EV-related services as compared to large companies. Impact is created through onboarding SMEs to promote the technologies developed in SmartCorners (“technology ambassador”).
- 5. Research Community:** advancing design methods and proposing new technologies for EVs and their systems / components, which are beyond state-of-the-art. Impact is created through interacting with the Research and Development (R&D) community to creating an open innovation ecosystem, supported by high quality public deliverables, high ranked scientific publications (open access).
- 6. Policy makers and European associations:** making policies and promoting strategies for eco-friendly road transport and smart mobility [7]. Impact is created through interactions with the policy makers relying on the project advances, (a) to challenge the new policies through technology evaluation, and (b) to provide technological recommendations on policies under preparation.

4 System Domain Analysis Methodology to draw users' profiles

The SmartCorners project aims to revolutionise EV design and operation through user-centric, adaptable, and energy-efficient SCS, incorporating IWMs and advanced control technologies. This ambitious project seeks to enhance vehicle performance and efficiency and contribute to a broader systemic change towards sustainable, decarbonised transport.

Policy interventions to foster the sector's electrification can help achieve various objectives—for example, air quality improvements and reduced GreenHouse Gas (GHG) emissions. However, addressing all key objectives—such as access to safe roads and liveable cities—requires a much broader package of measures. Linking and packaging policies are also essential to generate synergies between measures and align players.

Electric mobility needs to be embedded within an overarching approach that consists of several levels of intervention that shape not only vehicle technology but also mobility patterns and urban form. So, how can we adopt such an approach in practice? An integrated approach includes:

- **Technologies:** regarding EV technologies, there should be a clear focus on drastically downsizing vehicle size and power, fostering EE resources, and boosting cost-effectiveness. Various of these are addressed in the developments of the SCS. This is countering the trend of the last few decades towards bigger, faster, and more powerful cars, which has eradicated almost all efficiency gains in powertrain technologies. Only then will the electrification of the entire vehicle fleet be viable and affordable. In addition, EV concepts designed for shared use cases foster access and affordability. Technological innovations like automation must focus on complementarity with public transport systems. This is vital to public transport services' viability and encourages healthy and active mobility. Automation could be essential in providing on-demand mobility services in rural areas where traditional public transport options are not viable.
- **Infrastructure:** providing access for all to high-quality public transport services and infrastructure for walking and cycling is a vital part of a systemic approach to sustainable mobility. To enable this, compact city development can help with mixed-use, polycentric structures and short travel distances. A comprehensive network of charging solutions and reliable availability of charging points is crucial for a systemic change to drive a shift to EVs.
- **Services:** access to mobility services such as shared and ride-hailing services is another essential element for sustainable mobility. Services should be harmonised across available mobility services to encourage using the most efficient option. An SCS needs to cater to vehicles providing these services.
- **Users:** transport system users should have access to transparent information about the cost, time, safety and other relevant aspects of available mobility solutions and vehicles. Regulation of vehicle standards and technologies could further ensure that consumers have sufficient access to safe and efficient vehicles. Users feel confident with safer and more comfortable vehicles. SCS with skateboard chassis can enable vehicle design and technology advancements.

To align SmartCorners with the transformative approach required for decarbonising transport, the following vehicle design concept guidance is proposed:

Systemic Approach to Sustainable Mobility through SCS:

1. **Integrated Multi-Modal Transport Systems:** design SCS-equipped EVs to complement and integrate seamlessly with other modes of transportation, encouraging a shift away from less efficient vehicle use and towards more sustainable options like public transit, ride-sharing and sustainable urban logistics.
2. **User-Centric Design:** focus on understanding and meeting the diverse needs of users, including accessibility, comfort, safety, and convenience, to encourage the adoption of EVs and shared mobility services (PO-12, PO-13).
3. **Innovative Business Models:** develop business models that support shared mobility, Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS), and other services that reduce the need for private vehicle ownership and promote more efficient use of vehicles.

4.1 System Domain Analysis

System Domain Analysis (SDA) is a crucial process in system development. It involves studying the environment to identify factors that affect design, development, and implementation. Identifying and understanding stakeholders like end-users, administrators, regulators, and suppliers is essential.

This analysis examines the business processes the system will interact with or support. This includes mapping out existing workflows, identifying areas where improvements can be made, and understanding the organisation's or entities' goals and objectives. By gaining insights into the existing business processes, system designers can better align the system's capabilities with the needs and requirements of its users.

An important aspect is understanding the business organisation within the automotive supply chain. In the last decade, due to the different merging operations (e.g., Stellantis), the car manufacturers have further increased their buyer power over their supply chain due to the number of parts produced and the specificities of the developed vehicle platform. Due to the large investments required to design a new component and/or a new vehicle compliant with all relevant regulations, the entry barrier for new entrants is very high, and low-volume production that can address specific market needs is difficult to achieve. The design of the corner solution proposed in SCS intends to reverse this trend by providing more modularity and independence between the vehicle architecture and the single components. This is expected to provide more freedom for vehicle manufacturers to adapt and customise their platforms.

Additionally, SDA involves assessing the regulatory and compliance requirements that the system must adhere to. This includes understanding industry standards, legal frameworks, data protection regulations, and any other relevant guidelines that may impact the system's design and operation.

By conducting a thorough system domain analysis, stakeholders can ensure that the system is developed and implemented in a way that meets the needs of its users, complies with regulations, and aligns with organisational objectives.

4.2 Potential User Profiles

Considering the benefits of the SCS innovation, it is essential to ascertain the target groups that would benefit from it. The project concept broadly categorised the various target groups

that would benefit from the SmartCorners project, also elaborated in Section 0 above. Some initial benefits for these target groups are elaborated in this section.

One of the target groups that would benefit from the SCS innovation is the end user segment. It includes passenger car owners (or personal motor vehicle users), urban logistic vehicle operators and public transport companies and users, and shared mobility users (including taxis and ride-hailing services).

Passenger car users (including taxis and ride-hailing services):

Passenger or personal motor vehicle users benefit from SCS in the form of safer, more efficient, and easy-to-manoeuvre vehicles. The skateboard design allows wider cabins, and the IWMs and ASS enable tighter turning radius and improved handling, which is ideal for urban environments. Steer-by-wire allows personalised driving modes catering to comfort, agility, or EE. Finally, this results in a safer driving experience, more accessible parking and manoeuvring, higher energy efficiency, and potential cost savings compared to traditional EVs.

Public transport users:

Due to the flexibility offered by SCS innovation, the solution is adaptable to vehicles of various sizes. This also is an advantage for autonomous vehicles serving as public transport vehicles. Such autonomous vehicles can cater to the needs of underserved areas and expand public transport coverage. Due to the possibility of roomier cabins, public transport vehicles can accommodate people with accessibility needs. The SCS innovation will make public transport EVs more attractive to users and operators as they are more resource efficient.

Urban Logistics Operators:

With a growing need to shift urban logistics to cleaner and more efficient vehicles, EVs are replacing conventional delivery vehicles. While smaller deliveries are made by electric cargo bikes, there is still a need to use mid-sized trucks. In many cities, manoeuvring these mid-sized trucks is cumbersome. The SCS innovation will enable better manoeuvrability in the delivery vehicles. With the advent of autonomous vehicles, the SCS innovation will also benefit these vehicles. ASS ensures cargo stability and comfort and integration with logistics management systems for route optimisation and real-time tracking.

The benefits to OEMs and Automotive manufacturers through SCS innovation are apparent: efficient, safer, and better technology vehicles enable manufacturers to expand their market share when there is a high level of user acceptance. It is especially expected that SCS innovation will be an enabler for small and mid-size OEMs to efficiently enter the market/strengthen their position in the market and provide highly customised vehicle solutions addressing niche markets and being able to be integrated into a holistic mobility concept.

A favourable regulatory framework is an essential enabling factor for the widespread uptake of EVs and enabling innovation. The decision-makers and policymakers are instrumental in enabling such frameworks, which is possible through better awareness of the benefits of innovations such as SCS.

In addition to the above, some other actors that enable wider uptake of SCS are:

- a. Urban decision-makers, better aware of innovation, can pave the way for SCS's success by crafting a robust regulatory framework. This involves creating clear rules for new vehicle

types and autonomous operations and addressing safety, licensing, and insurance concerns. Additionally, adapting existing infrastructure standards to accommodate the unique features of SmartCorners vehicles, like tighter turning radius and charging needs, is crucial. Finally, establishing data privacy and security regulations will ensure user trust and responsible data handling, fostering a positive environment for innovation and adoption.

- b. Smart city infrastructure is key to seamlessly integrate SmartCorners vehicles. This means building a strong Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication network for information exchange, installing charging stations in strategic locations for easy power access, and designating dedicated lanes or zones for efficient public transport and logistics. Additionally, encouraging the use of EVs through parking incentives for personal and shared programs will further reduce traffic congestion and pollution. By taking these steps, urban planners can create a conducive environment for SmartCorners, reducing congestion, improving air quality, ensuring efficient public transport and logistics, and creating a more sustainable transportation system for everyone.
- c. Collaborating with private companies and research institutions can accelerate the development and testing of SCS in specific areas. Financial incentives like subsidies can encourage early technology adoption by public transport operators, logistics companies, and car-sharing programs. Public education campaigns can inform citizens about the benefits and safety features of SCS, addressing potential concerns and encouraging broader acceptance.

In the following stages, the SmartCorners project will explore a more in-depth dialogue and participation from various stakeholders to establish a robust use case and explore users' needs in various geographies to expand the market outreach of the SCS innovation.

5 High-level description of the SmartCorners components

Smart Corners functionalities are granted by the interaction and synergy between the four main subsystems outlined in the following subsections:

- *In-wheel motor.*
- *Active shock absorber.*
- *Suspension control arms with sensorized components.*
- *Camber, toe and trackwidth controlled chassis actuators.*

In the following pages each subsystem is analysed, and a high-level description of their main components is presented.

5.1 In-wheel motor

Among all the possible configurations, EVs equipped with IWMs seem promising since intelligent traction control can be implemented to improve both propulsion and vehicle dynamics (PO-01). The powertrain also acts as a chassis actuator, allowing full control torque distribution, i.e. the so-called TVC [8] (PO-02). Furthermore, IWMs can assure high-torque and power density directly applied to the vehicle wheel, assuring higher efficiency of the system due to no reduction stage in between motor and road, and high stiffness of the transmission.

IWMs can be implemented with various electromagnetic layouts, which differ in robustness, performance, bandwidth, functionality, scalability, and cost. The predominant structures in the current technology landscape are:

- Radial flux, direct-drive machines
- Radial flux, geared machines
- Radial flux, dual airgap direct-drive machines

Figure 4: Elaphe L-type v5 IWM is a radial flux direct-drive machine.

Axial flux machines are often proposed for IWM use, however intrinsic robustness challenges of axial flux machines are much more emphasized in the environment of wheel rim, which makes them a difficult technology to implement. Therefore, axial flux machines are at this point not successfully implemented in IWMs.

The IWM structure used in this project by Elaphe is the radial flux, direct drive machine with a dislocated inverter (on sprung mass). The latter choice is influenced by cost, scalability and High Voltage (HV) safety considerations (Figure 5).

Figure 5: BMW i3 crash-test [9] depicting a potential HV safety risk scenario for IWM with integrated inverter (wheel detachment).

For the project objectives (PO-03), the main features of the selected radial flux, direct-drive machine (L-type v5; Figure 4) are related to:

- Efficiency, focused on partial load losses and controllability.
- Millisecond response time and ability to change the torque direction seamlessly.
- Integration, allowing other chassis actuator components and suspension components to be integrated with the IWM (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Integration layout of the Elaphe IWM.

5.2 Active shock absorber

Due to the presence of an IWM the suspension role is fundamental to mitigate the effect of the unsprung mass increment. A full ASS represents the best solution to this issue, allowing to directly apply forces also at high frequency, heavily impacting on the dynamics of both sprung and unsprung mass. Furthermore, this kind of system can achieve significant benefits for comfort, vehicle handling and energy consumption, allowing both active and regenerative operations.

An ASA can be realized exploiting different technologies. Linear electric motors (EMs) could look like a natural candidate, but due to their limited force density rotary solutions are preferred. Nevertheless, a linear-to-rotary motion conversion is then needed and can be achieved through electro-hydrostatic or electromechanical solutions. The first ones act on the suspension by means of a pump and a hydraulic piston, while the second ones instead exploit a linkage system connected to the suspension itself.

In SmartCorners environment, electromechanical solutions may be preferred because oil-free, but they also present several advantages compared to hydraulic solutions, in terms of energy conversion efficiency, inertia, packaging, frequency bandwidth, simplicity and reliability (PO-09).

The main components of an electromechanical ASA are:

- *a linkage*, connecting the suspension to the damping actuator, transforming linear motion into angular displacement.
- *a gearbox*, placed between the lever and the EM, multiplying the angular speed to allow an efficient operation of the motor.
- *an EM*, delivering the torque needed to aid or counteract the suspension linear motion.

Figure 7: ASA working principle diagram [10].

The EM technology and its design are defined by operating conditions within mechanical, electrical, and thermal physical domains [10]. To satisfy envelope requirements of the damper and fit inside the vehicle corner, compactness is crucial. So, superficial permanent-magnet synchronous machines are usually selected because of their distinctive high torque density.

The sizing of the EM is related mainly to envelope and overall transmission ratio. The first one guides the cross-section design of the machine, while the latter, defined once the required damping is determined from vehicle system requirements, determines the axial active length of the motor.

The linkage design is heavily dependent from the whole suspension architecture. It must guarantee no interference with other components along the whole suspension stroke, while minimizing the linkage transmission ratio to achieve the fixed overall ratio with a lower gearbox contribution. Another fundamental parameter in its design is the transmission angle,

which defines the linkage quality, that should be kept as near as possible to 90° in nominal position and should be limited in the range between 40° and 140°, as recommended in literature [11]. Self-locking issues could arise outside the recommended angular stroke.

Once the linkage geometry has been determined, the gearbox's transmission ratio is known. Together with envelope constraints it is the main parameter for the speed reducer choice and design. Given the usually high transmission ratios required, the most common choices are double-stage planetary [10] or single-stage cycloidal speed reducers. Other important aspects to be considered during the gearbox design are of course efficiency, inertia, backlash, noise, shock-load, and fatigue capacity. All these properties have an impact on the whole damper effectiveness and the perception and comfort of the final user.

SmartCorners envisions the implementation of system-level design approaches, where the design requirements arise from vehicle dynamics manoeuvre simulations. In this way, the complete device schematized conceptually in Figure 7 can be sized according to realistic working conditions. Moreover, a suitable sizing is carried out on all the relevant components: a coordinated design effort is needed to identify a global optimal configuration.

5.3 Suspension control arm with sensorized components

When using IWMs for propulsion, the wheel assembly mass must be reduced to accommodate for the contribution of the machine. Structural elements of the suspension system can be lightened using FRP composite materials. The strength of these elements must be sufficient to guarantee user safety during the exchange of large forces among the SCS elements. Being the control arms safety and structural suspension parts, the FRP material can be modified with highly conductive carbon-based particles that activate a self-sensing mechanism. Structural health can be monitored through the self-sensing signals, which can be processed in real time through AI-based algorithms. The objective is to estimate the integrity of components by sensing the electrical resistance of the material at specific points to predict possible failures.

The smart sensing technology is constituted by three core sub-systems:

- *Self-sensing material*: the embedding of carbon nanoparticles or microparticles into the polymer composite creates a conductive network within the polymer matrix that can be used to detect changes in the material resistivity due to applied mechanical loads.
- *Acquisition system*: the resistivity measurements require a designed interface that can acquire the signal from the structural component and communicate with the Engine Control Unit (ECU).
- *AI-based processing algorithm*: measurement samples must be processed with a parametric integrity estimation method that is calibrated on the monitored part.

Marelli will develop a new lightweight composite suspension control arm integrating SHM system. The proposed solution is based on a self-sensing technology which represents a trade-off between complexity and product cost targeting automotive applications for mass production. It is expected to reach at least 30% mass saving compared to a benchmark normal production component.

Figure 8: Composite suspension prototype with SHM system.

Marelli will also contribute into the project to re-design those structural suspension elements impacted by the IWM integration (knuckle and upper control arm). Indeed, depending on the final suspension architecture, IWM impacts either in terms of available design space and local mass increase, as already mentioned in previous paragraphs. The proper combination of lightweight composite materials and metal, through dedicated product development workflows, allows the possibility to better exploit the available design space and compensate for IWM induced mass increase.

5.4 Camber, toe and trackwidth controlled chassis systems

Advanced chassis systems can be categorized for different functionalities:

1. For enhanced vehicle performance.
2. For enhanced vehicle manoeuvrability.

The chassis system to enhanced vehicle performance can be divided into (PO-07, PO-08):

- Adjusting the wheel camber (vertical axle of the wheels relative to the vertical axis), this system adjusts the wheel camber up to 3° during heavy cornering of the vehicle to optimise tire contact patch. During braking the tire camber can be adjusted to less camber, mainly in combination with adjusting the wheel toe, differently for front and rear tyres.

Figure 9: Dynamic camber adjustment University student project 2010.

- Wheel toe adjustment is a system to dynamically change the angle of the wheels relative to the longitudinal axis of the vehicles, this is to reduce rolling resistance in straight line driving and improve grip during acceleration and deceleration. Precise adjustment of

camber and toe can improve tire wear and extending tire life while reducing the rolling resistance and thus improving energy consumption.

- Adjusting trackwidth: this system is adjusting the distance between the left and right tire) of the vehicle. This system is enhancing vehicle stability during cornering.

Figure 10: TRIGGO [12]

The second key feature that an advanced chassis systems can achieve is to improve manoeuvrability of the vehicle. There is a trend of increased wheelbase by dedicated Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) chassis to house the battery pack between the wheel corners.

On the other hand, urban environments are characterized by congested streets, narrow lanes, and frequent stops and more effort is required to manoeuvre the vehicle. Therefore, the ability to turn the wheels to a wider angle enhances the vehicle's overall manoeuvrability. Wide-angle steering systems are particularly beneficial at low speeds. It allows drivers to negotiate sharp corners, make quick direction changes, and perform complex parking manoeuvres with greater ease and precision, even in congested or confined spaces. Wide-angle steering systems allow the wheels to turn to a greater angle compared to traditional steering systems.

Figure 11: RWTH concept SpeedE [13].

The proposed SCS is combining all the above-mentioned features by varying the wishbone lengths, and depending on the chosen configuration, is capable of:

- Full suspension travel up to 800 mm.
- Active steering angles of $\pm 50^\circ$.
- Active camber angles of $\pm 30^\circ$.
- Active Track Width from 2000 mm to 2600 mm.

Following Work Packages (WPs) will determine the most efficient and effective way to use the actuation system for the given vehicle segments.

6 User-centric vehicle control functionalities

IWMs demonstrate a markedly superior torque response rate compared to conventional powertrain systems. This advantage is primarily attributed to three factors: the reduced rotational inertia between the rotor and the tire, and the omission of both shaft and gearbox from the system. Rotational inertia, the metric quantifying an object's resistance to changes in its rotational state, is significantly minimized in IWM configurations. This is because the motor directly actuates the wheel, eliminating the need for intermediary components that contribute additional mass and complexity. Such a direct linkage facilitates more rapid torque adjustments, thereby enhancing the vehicle's responsiveness. Moreover, the absence of a shaft and gearbox mitigates mechanical losses and delays commonly observed in traditional systems, where torque transmission through shaft torsion stiffness and multiple gear stages before wheel engagement introduces inefficiencies. Gearboxes, while integral to conventional drivetrains, increase complexity and weight, and generate a latency in torque delivery due to shaft torsional stiffness, gear backlash and mechanical losses. Hence, by excluding these elements, IWMs ensure instantaneous torque availability, markedly improving torque controllability.

Figure 12: Left (A) conventional central drivetrain torque response reaching 2250Nm reference torque in 400ms [14]. Right (B) Elaphe direct drive IWM reaching 1000Nm in less than 4ms.

The unique capability of IWMs to facilitate immediate torque sign changes—transitioning seamlessly between positive and negative torque—further underscores their superiority. This attribute, a direct consequence of foregoing a gearbox, significantly augments the agility and control of EVs. In traditional drivetrains, gearboxes are pivotal in torque transmission and modulation; however, their mechanical components introduce inertia and delay, complicating rapid torque direction shifts and increasing wear. In contrast, IWMs' direct motor-to-wheel coupling circumvents these mechanical limitations, enabling swift torque reversal crucial for functions that requires high frequency torque oscillations. Additionally, the direct drive nature of IWMs implies that rapid torque sign changes do not compromise motor durability. Without mechanical gears susceptible to stress from quick engagements and disengagements, the system is not prone to wear, thus enhancing the operational lifespan and reducing maintenance needs.

Figure 13: Left (A) Elaphe direct drive IWM showing that rotor is directly connected to rim and brake. Right (B) conventional central motor that rotates the gears and the shafts before transmitting torque to the wheel.

Beyond the immediate benefits of IWMs [15], their role in generating vertical forces through interaction with the suspension system's Instantaneous Centre of Rotation (ICR) and motor mounting position offers further advantages. When an IWM applies torque, it not only propels the vehicle forward but also impacts the vertical dynamics of the wheel assembly. The specific suspension geometry, particularly the ICR's position, allows applied torque to induce vertical forces on the chassis. This mechanism enables the IWM, by adjusting its torque, to leverage the suspension geometry for exerting vertical forces that either counterbalance or enhance the natural suspension response.

Figure 14: Side view of a wheel with longitudinal and vertical forces, instantaneous centre of the wheel vertical movement and RB-angle [16].

The integration of direct drive IWM benefits with strategic torque application, in harmony with the suspension's geometric characteristics, facilitates refined control over the vehicle's vertical dynamics (PO-02, PO-03). By adeptly modulating these vertical forces in conjunction with the ICR, the system can proactively mitigate the effects of road imperfections, and significantly improve occupant comfort [17]. The result obtained in [17] demonstrates the reduction of the vertical acceleration of the sprung mass of human-sensitive frequency range of between 4-8 Hz, improving ride comfort by properly designing a filter for motor drive (Figure 15). Furthermore, such active vertical force controls by IWMs can downsize the required active suspension actuator, further reducing the overall cost and unsprung mass [18]. This sophisticated interplay between IWMs, and carefully designed suspension geometries heralds

a notable advancement in ride comfort and vehicle stability, representing a considerable leap in automotive engineering.

Figure 15: Power spectrum density of vertical acceleration of sprung mass [17].

One of the main components of the SCS are the IWMs, which has the peculiarity of taking up little space, leaving more available to the frame, thus allowing the use of the skateboard layout (Figure 1a, PO-01). Another advantage of using IWMs on 4 Wheel Drive (4WD) layout is that they allow individual control of the torque on the 4 wheels. Given the importance of the component, a literature review was carried out on the control systems used to increase the EE of EV using TVC. For the review, papers from 2010 onwards, published only in English language were considered, and it was also observed that the patents published on EETVC do not report the analytical formulations of the controllers and EE optimization algorithms. The histogram plot highlights that the EETVC technique has a sharp increase in published papers since 2017, probably attributed to the growing presence of EVs. The peak of published documents, is between 2020 and 2021, highlighting the fact that we have now entered the industrialization phase of the previously developed technologies.

Figure 16: Number of published papers per year about EETVC.

Depending on the performance required from the EV, in the literature review the papers are divided in different groups based on the vehicle layout:

1. Front Wheel Drive (FWD) EV.

2. Rear Wheel Drive (RWD) EV.
3. Four Wheel Drive (4WD) EV.

For each of this configuration, the EM can be placed on-board (being part of the sprung mass) or in-wheel (being part of the unsprung mass).

Automakers are racing towards vehicle electrification to comply with the recent Zero CO₂ emission target for new cars and vans starting from 2035. However, the EVs' market share needs that such vehicles can also provide superior functionality at competitive costs, such as EM responsiveness. Therefore, an evolution of EV architectures is expected to improve range, performance, agility, safety, and comfort, while also reducing the vehicle complexity.

These results are achievable with a breakthrough approach based on the so-called skateboard platform concept (Figure 1a) in combination with the SmartCorners solution (Figure 1b).

To implement a user-centric vehicle control strategy, it is essential to be able to control as many variables as possible and ensuring that the behaviour of the vehicle varies depending on the user's preferences.

The literature review reports the analysis and the analytical formulation of the vehicle control system used to increase the EE of EV as follows. The most widespread strategy is the Control Allocation (CA) algorithm that aims to optimally distribute wheel torques to enhance vehicle stability, EE and overall vehicle performance. The CA algorithm can be implemented offline or online. In the former one, the control strategy is typically computed during the vehicle design or development phase, and it is often stored in Look-Up Table (LUT) or pre-defined maps. In the latter case, the CA strategy is directly integrated into the vehicle, adjusting the torque distribution to respond to changing conditions, e.g. road conditions and driver input. The main advantage of the online implementation, w.r.t. the offline case, is that there is no need for a large amount of memory to store maps or LUT. On the other hand, it is required a quick response of the processor to changes in the vehicle dynamics.

Another approach is the Rule-Based Control Allocation (RBCA). In this case, the strategy is formulated in the form of "if-else" flow chart, to explore different wheel torque combinations, which satisfy predefined logical rules aimed to select the best operational mode based on the demanded torque. The approach is the same in cornering and in straight-line conditions, with the difference that, in the former one, the torque is optimally distributed between the left and the right wheel, while, in the latter one, the wheel torque is optimally distributed between the front and the rear axles. The result obtained in [19] demonstrates that in an EV with multiple drivetrains, the powertrain power losses are minimized with the progressive activation of an increasing number of EMs, with evenly distributed torque (Figure 17).

A different approach, called "Optimization-Based Control Allocation (OBCA) algorithm" focuses on the optimization and minimization of the tire energy dissipation, from both lateral and longitudinal forces, and of the EM power consumption. The OBCA problem is formulated as a minimization of allocation error and control actuations.

Figure 17: Total power loss as a function of the total torque demand for different number of activated EMs $n_{d,EM}$ (from [19]).

All the methods previously seen are methods that act because of the request. The improvement of the EE based on the prediction of the future states of the vehicle involves the implementation of MPC algorithms, but only a limited subset addresses the aspect of EE within the optimization problem. There are different typologies of MPC algorithms. The one that comes closest to reality because it also considers the vehicle and tire non-linearities, is the NMPC. The aim of the MPC algorithm is to calculate an optimal sequence of input designed to minimize a cost function that incorporates the prediction of the system dynamics along the prediction horizon. For EE purposes, the cost function implemented in the MPC is aimed at minimizing both tracking error and power losses. In the NMPC, the cost function usually incorporates the tire slip power loss, the electric powertrain power loss, and the friction power loss.

A complementary approach to enhance the EE of an EV is to define a target understeer characteristic, different w.r.t. the baseline one (or passive, without TVC). Generally, TVC algorithms alter the cornering behaviour of a vehicle by allocating torques to the wheels in an optimal manner to enhance both stability and EE. Simulations on 4WD vehicle with constant traction force distribution show that the understeer characteristic is influenced by the longitudinal acceleration a_x , with an understeer behaviour for positive longitudinal acceleration values and oversteer behaviour for negative longitudinal acceleration values.

Figure 18: Understeer characteristics evaluated for different values of longitudinal acceleration [20].

Regarding the power losses, the understeer characteristic that minimizes the lateral tire slip power loss is close to the neutral steering behaviour, while the longitudinal tire slip power loss is minimized for an understeer characteristic that is closer to the optimal one in term of input power, with a marginally less understeering behaviour than the baseline one.

In modern passenger cars, another typology of chassis' actuation is represented by active suspension control [21]. The ASS is normally used for reducing the low-frequency motion of the sprung mass during acceleration, deceleration, and cornering – i.e. pitch and roll motion, for increasing passengers' comfort when riding on uneven surfaces, and for road holding control. The ASS also allows the control of the front-rear anti-roll moment distribution. Moreover, integrated TVC and ASS control could enhance the cornering response and EE with respect to the independent control of the actuators. So, the ASS generates the anti-roll moment contribution. In [21] the NMPC controller is coupled with the ASS for roll moment compensation generating a force contribution.

Another point that could be developed on this kind of layout (skateboard platform Figure 1a) is the integrated control of multi-actuator [22]. For example, the actuator can be placed on each wheel, can influence the camber angle and the normal force. The multi-actuator configuration allows to use various subsystems to generate control demand for the compensation of control errors. This approach allows to obtain a high EE action and a good vehicle dynamics' control.

All this kind of control strategies do not consider the driver profile in such a way as to optimise propulsion system by making it user centric.

One of the aims of SmartCorners project, is to fill the gap between the current control strategies and the user-centric vehicle control functionalities. Keep going on research about vehicle connectivity and integration of advanced sensor with real-time data, could allow a more accurate torque distribution based on driving conditions, road topography, vehicle load distribution and other possible dynamic factors. Potential benefits can be achieved from the integration of energy efficient NNMPC with AI DTs (PO-12, PO-13) and from the adoption of novel TVC functions. Another approach is to increase the precision of the Vehicle-To-Infrastructure (V2I) communication to obtain road surface adhesion coefficient, road roughness and other information (PO-10). In addition, TVC could be integrated with autonomous driving systems to further improve vehicle safety and stability during autonomous manoeuvres (PO-11). This could include better torque management when changing lanes, crossing intersection and other complex situations. An interesting possibility could be coupling with DRL strategy to train autonomous driving systems.

7 User-centric - AI Supported Thermal and Cabin comfort controls

The thermal management of EVs is a widely researched topic [23], which involves the control of the temperature of vehicle components, in particular batteries [24], [25] and/or the passenger compartment [26], for the comfort and safety of the driver. In recent years, improvements on the hardware side have been made to reduce energy consumption, for example by introducing heat pumps and thermal preconditioning, heat recovery systems for powertrain/electrical components [27], thermal energy storage systems (which are expected to increase heating efficiency only marginally) and thermal panels (see Figure 19a and tested by Ford [28] and Lexus, for example).

To fully exploit the potential of any configuration, the behaviour of all subsystems must be simultaneously optimized and adapted to changing conditions, and ideally integrated with the vehicle's energy management system [24]. However, due to the inherent complexity and corresponding computational difficulties, few studies have addressed the optimization of the overall energy consumption of a vehicle [29]. Lajunen [27] proposed an integrated thermal management system for an EV that takes into account the passenger compartment, battery and powertrain. Experimental results showed that the range increased by almost 32% in winter conditions, despite the use of simple controllers for each subcomponent. Other researchers have demonstrated efficiency gains using advanced control methods that include predictive control. For example, an intelligent MPC (IMPC) strategy has been proposed that combines prediction of vehicle speed and passenger thermal comfort for an AC cabin system [29] (Figure 19b). For the same driving cycle (WLTC) at an ambient temperature of $\sim 38^{\circ}\text{C}$, IMPC achieved the highest thermal comfort and reduced the energy consumption of the air conditioning system by 25.6% compared to the PID controller and by 4.3% compared to the MPC strategy.

Figure 19: Schematic diagrams of a) the placement of infrared radiant warmers with a cabin; b) intelligent MPC for an AC-cabin system [29]; c) Tesla thermal management system heating modes [30].

ML-based control strategies and AI-based predictions of operating conditions (e.g., battery temperature [29]) have also been successfully proposed. A key aspect for all developed solutions is the accurate simulation of personal thermal comfort. To this end, several researchers propose AI-based thermal comfort models [27], [29]. In more severe climates, significant energy savings can be achieved by properly preconditioning systems. Tesla's thermal management system (nicknamed "Octovalve [30]"), for example, has several heating modes, some of which are used for preconditioning (Figure 19c). The system is able to reduce EV power consumption and battery load during warm-up, but at the expense of overall warm-up time. A 2023 review study [24] concludes that smart controls combining online big data, user characteristics, current and future road state information, and current and future weather information have shown promise for improving the EE of EV thermal management systems. The ability to integrate all systems and an approach to use additional information is the main ambition of SmartCorners. We are designing a holistic and predictive thermal management system that is highly adaptive to environmental conditions. Novel, fast-running artificial intelligence models will be created to accurately predict conditions and quickly control system components. The system includes pre-conditioning functions for the main powertrain components and the passenger compartment to balance the trade-off between user experience and energy consumption in different climatic conditions.

One of the main objectives of the SCS is to provide energy-optimised heating/cooling and dehumidification concepts and components through intelligent control, without compromising the thermal comfort of the passenger compartment (PO-04, PO-05, PO-06). EVs have a complex thermal interface layout as shown in Figure 20. The thermal conditioning circuits, such as the coolant and refrigerant circuits, are composed of several elements. On the other hand, the subsystems of the passenger compartment, battery and drive train require different constraints to be met. The holistic approach in this proposal describes the thermal subsystems shown in Figure 20 using high-fidelity 1-dimensional models (networks) that accurately represent the system under steady-state and transient conditions. The resulting model is used to perform two main tasks:

1. Accurately reproduce the energy efficiency of the thermal system.
2. A thorough assessment of the thermal comfort of the occupants.

Figure 20: Thermal system interfaces on a vehicle model.

For the first task, the simulation model includes all the actuators of the thermal system, i.e. pumps, valves, fans, heat exchangers, etc. The engagement condition of each actuator is crucial to understand the behaviour of the system, and to recognise that this results in a trade-off between cooling performance and energy efficiency of the system. The cost functions required for optimisation can be designed to achieve optimal compromises, while taking into account the actuator engagement level from an energy point of view.

The second task focuses on user-centred thermal comfort. The cabin model will require accurate flow and temperature distribution. Other factors such as radiation, humidity and CO2 concentration are also needed. For this purpose, a combination of 3D CFD and thermal simulation will be used. This knowledge leads to improved control strategies for passenger compartment air conditioning, window humidification, fresh air intake, etc. A passenger model is needed to determine comfort values. This occupant model, together with the environmental conditions, produces an indication of thermal comfort based on the input values listed in Table 3. Information on the previous activity of the person's well-being is also important. Passengers with a persistently elevated heart rate tend to warm up quickly and recent physical activity also affects comfort. Therefore, this data can be collected by a smart wearable device and processed together with cabin data using AI algorithms. This fusion of information will result in more accurate values for key performance indices for thermal comfort and energy efficiency.

Table 3: Thermal comfort values.

Variable	Target
Cabin temperature	Comfort range (22-25 °C)
Ambient surface temperature	$(T_{surf} - T_{air}) \leq 4 \text{ °C}$
Humidity	Comfort range (30-70%)
Air speed	$\leq 15 \text{ m/s}$
Air turbulence intensity	$< 20\%$, fluctuation $> 2 \text{ Hz}$
Activity rate	Sitting, Driving (1-1.3)
Clothing	Case dependent

To speed up real-time simulation, high-fidelity models are reduced to Fast Running Models (FRMs). With appropriate experimental design methods, inputs can be systematically stimulated to understand their relationship to output measures of comfort and efficiency. The thermal control strategy can be structured as shown in Figure 21: . Parallel AI and non-AI paths are implemented to manage thermal control. The goal is to exploit AI as much as possible, while using a simple and autonomous control architecture that can be easily tested and validated on a few prototype vehicles, leading to a reduction in development cost and effort. To train the AI-based control layer, real data of the system under test is needed under different working conditions. Another challenging aspect is the definition of an appropriate reward function that optimizes the system as desired. For this purpose, variable scenarios can be generated in the simulation environment. Reinforcement learning guidelines are recorded to obtain iterative training data. Once convergence is ensured, the trained controller can be applied to the vehicle. However, the learning process does not stop there: real data captured

by the vehicle can be used to continue the iterative learning process. This re-learning cycle bridges the gap between simulation and reality and includes specific driver behaviour data that was not available at the model level. In this way, user-centric comfort is personalised for each individual user. This example requires the following key components, as illustrated in Figure 22: :

Figure 21: Thermal control strategy block diagram.

Figure 22: Training diagram for holistic thermal and energy management.

1. IT infrastructure to simulate and train control policy, deploy it into the vehicle, collect real data and retrain the policy.
2. Several realistic driver models to train the developed strategy in different situations. Simulations allow fast and cost-effective training, if the dynamic models are sufficiently realistic.
3. A training monitoring framework that provides a visual and intuitive understanding of the convergence and evolution of the reward function during the training process.

In this process, dehumidification and de-misting strategies will also be thoroughly investigated. The AI strategy receives relevant information (e.g. CO₂ content, humidity, presence of fog) to adjust the fresh and optimal ratio of fresh to circulated air.

8 Technical impact categories

The SmartCorners project is harmoniously integrated into the emerging technological trend in designing EVs that is characterized by increased integration of chassis and powertrain components / systems into the modular wheel assembly. The interest of OEMs and suppliers to this topic can be confirmed by recent conceptual wheel corner technologies, e.g., demonstrated by Hyundai (2023) and Continental (2024), Figure 23, as well as flexible “POD - corner” architectures of EVs. These aspects allow identifying several technical impact categories relevant to the SmartCorners assets.

Figure 23: Wheel corner concepts of Hyundai Mobis (top, [31]) and Continental (bottom, [32] [Link](#)).

Technical impact from wheel corner design to different industrial sub-sectors:

1. Targeting automotive OEMs to address demand of private and business users for affordable and reliable EVs, well integrated in mobility platforms for additional services; SmartCorners intends to address both traditional OEMs as well as emerging OEMs with high agility to address highly customized solutions.
2. Targeting automotive suppliers and engineering companies to address demand on rapid creation of innovations in EV systems and components as well as related technologies, engineering services and data-driven services for road e-mobility.
3. Targeting SME sector to address increasing positions as a more agile and latitudinous driver of innovations in emerging EV components and EV-related services as compared to large companies.

The technologies characterizing the SCS impact on several vehicle aspects both as a single control element and as a synergic system. Those aspects mainly involve *safety* and vehicle dynamics *performances* based on the higher-level user-centric control. Particularly, vehicle performances can split into *comfort*, *handling*, and *efficiency*, which can be considered as independent at first approximation. Table 4 summarizes the relevance of each SCS on these aspects.

Table 4: Technical impact of each SCS component.

Strong influence	Secondary influence	No influence
PP	P	O

	In-wheel motor	Active shock absorber	Active camber and toe control	Sensorised suspension arms
Safety	P	PP	P	PP
Comfort	PP	PP	O	P
Handling	PP	PP	PP	P
Efficiency	PP	PP	P	O
Tire management	P	PP	PP	P

Safety

As the suspension is a critical safety component for the vehicle, fail-safe strategies and physical implementations must be included to reach homologation. In particular, the ASA must exhibit fail-safe modes to guarantee a minimum level of damping in case of any electrical or logical failure.

The sensorized suspension arms are also crucial for real-time stress monitoring since they will be subjected not only to the usual loads from road and chassis but also to additional loads due to the control actions of the other SCS components. Once the estimated stress reaches a certain threshold, the vehicle must switch to an emergency status, limiting the reachable speed and warning for an urgent intervention.

Safety is also involved in vehicle stability, especially in emergency manoeuvres. To this end, IWMs could be properly controlled during braking to avoid any tire lock, responsive yaw control useful during emergency manoeuvres can be obtained by controlling toe angle [33] and with proper TVC [34].

Eventually, in case of heavy bumps or potholes, the ASA can act on the tire to guarantee a constant contact with the ground, thus vehicle control by the driver.

Comfort

The starting point is the non-negligible increase of the unsprung mass due to the presence of an IWM, which translates in the shift of the unsprung mass resonance to lower frequencies at constant tire stiffness, hence in larger amplitude both for the sprung mass acceleration response and for the tire deflection frequency response to road input [35]. Typically, IWMs add about 30 kg to the unsprung mass, so its resonance frequency shift from around 11-12 Hz to 9-10 Hz for a reference SUV quarter car. This phenomenon worsens the ride comfort performance of the vehicle because it brings larger sprung mass acceleration gains nearer to the human-sensitive frequency range of 4-8 Hz, as established by ISO 2631 [36].

Ride comfort can be addressed by a proper control of the ASA. The minimization of the sprung mass acceleration is the usual control objective, often emphasizing minimization at low frequencies until 8. The control action is a force acting in parallel with the primary suspension stiffness and it can both generate power into the suspension or filter the one coming from road.

For low frequency – i.e. 1-2 Hz – sprung mass motions, that are strongly linked to motion sickness, IWM torque control can be exploited, too; in fact, motor rigid connection to the wheel guarantees a good actuation bandwidth and longitudinal acceleration is strictly related to pitch torque generation. This control action can be superimposed to the traction control action by summing different harmonic contributions.

Handling

As already introduced, the increase of the unsprung mass due to the IWM causes larger tire deflection amplitudes, leading to highly variable tire vertical force and possible wheel detachment from ground when travelling on irregular roads (PO-10). This reflects on handling performances since tire cornering stiffness is almost linearly dependent to the vertical load before saturation; therefore, vertical load control is important to impose an under- or oversteering behaviour to the vehicle. Road holding can be controlled by minimizing the tire deflection since vertical tire behaviour can be modelled as a spring between the unsprung mass and the road contact. The outcome is a vertical force as constant as possible guaranteeing tire grip in all driving conditions.

Vehicle handling performances can be addressed by suspension geometry control, too. Controlled suspension arms can adapt toe and camber angles to driving conditions. Considering the front axle, toe-in enhances straight line high-speed driving because the vehicle results more understeering; on the contrary, toe-out makes the vehicle more responsive to steering. Considering the rear axle, toe control can enable rear wheel steering and, consequently, more agile behaviour in urban scenarios, and higher cornering capability at high speed. Moreover, rear wheel steering allows crab steering mode, useful for parking in narrow spaces.

Lateral force generation can be exploited also by active camber control (PO-11) for enhancing vehicle yaw stability [37] and to actively influence the cornering stiffness of each corner.

Efficiency

Nowadays, automotive industry has an important role in reducing worldwide carbon footprint and pollution. Even if EVs eliminate tailpipe emissions, optimization of the power flows must be considered for reducing the overall impact of the industry and of the fleet. Proper torque allocation on each of the four wheels can be tuned in such a way to favour the overall energy consumption of the vehicle and guarantee at the same time the proper longitudinal forces [38]. The intrinsic regenerative functionality of the ASA can ensure energy recovery from road irregularities when working as a damper. Therefore, the average power consumption can be limited adding power to the control objective, although it is also intrinsic for damping force requests coming from whichever strategy.

Furthermore, camber control can potentially be beneficial to vehicle efficiency during cornering because it influences tire rolling resistance [39].

Tire management

Vehicle dynamics is dominated by the interaction between the ground and the tires. First, the vertical load creates a contact patch, then actuations on the wheel can stretch it order to generate stresses thus forces. In particular, the IWM generates slip for longitudinal forces, and steering and suspension geometry actuators generates lateral forces and aligning moments.

Nevertheless, excessive stresses in the tire can cause fast wear and continuous changes of the contact patch shape boosts the intrinsic hysteretic nature of the tire, hence rolling resistance [40].

In the end, the SCS could act on the contact patch finding a good trade-off between performances, wear, and losses.

Synergy

The most important feature of the SCS is the integration of all its components not only as a physical optimized assembly, but also as an intelligent integrated actuator for the chassis.

It is well known that ride comfort and road holding are conflicting objectives [41], but multi-objective control techniques can find good trade-off solutions and additional control purposes can be pursued; for example, the electromechanical coupling between electromagnetic excitations in the IWM and transient dynamics of the corner could be also addressed [42]. Low frequency sprung mass dynamics and high frequency dynamics due to the unsprung mass can be also simultaneously attenuated by developing full vehicle controllers [43]. This is extremely important for safety because pitch motion is involved in braking and can unload rear tires, and roll motion is involved in cornering and can unload in-the-bend tires. So, synergy between all the above-described features must be chased in the control design.

Moreover, the sections above and Table 4 highlights the presence of different actuators having the same impacts; so, the need of high-level supervision and coordination strategies [8] becomes crucial.

Finally, another important synergy arises from the sensorized suspension arms because real-time stress estimation of the components permits tire force estimation, thus force feedback for SCS controls, which nowadays is one of the highest obstacles in ASS deployment.

9 Conclusion

SmartCorners' main objective is to push the boundaries of innovation by accelerating the deployment of sustainable and user-centric e-mobility.

In the case of the SmartCorners project, in agreement with the entire consortium, it was decided to take the SUV as the type of vehicle on which to mount the innovative system. The simulations will be carried out on b-segment vehicles.

The vehicle architecture taken into consideration is the skateboard platform (Figure 1a) with 4 IWMs, which allows the increasing of the space available on the vehicle and in the trunk. Furthermore, the use of 4 IWMs allows better control of the torque at the wheels, improving performance, comfort, and handling. To reduce the weight of the vehicle and of the wheel assembly, the structural parts of the suspension are made of FRP.

The SmartCorners project will fill the gap in the state-of-the-art on vehicle control strategies, thanks to innovative AI-based control strategies with a user-centric approach, that will consider the state of wear of the vehicle and the user's driving conditions. Hence, to improve passengers' comfort and preserve vehicle structural health, the vehicle actuators controls, such as IWM, ASS, and ASA controls, will be adaptable to each user profile. Moreover, SCS will be implemented for different users' categories, such as passenger car users, public transport users and urban logistics. A focus will also be on EE aspects.

Considering all the factors shown in the previous chapters, the goal of creating a sustainable vehicle, adaptable to any type of segment and adaptable to any type of user, is achievable, heavily contributing to European development and innovation.

9.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

For this deliverable of the SmartCorners project and related task (T1.1), no recovery actions are required as there have been no deviations from the initial project and from the grant agreement.

10 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
4WD	4 Wheel Drive
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASA	Active Shock Absorber
ASS	Active Suspension System
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
CA	Control Allocation
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DT	Digital Twin
ECU	Engine Control Unit
EE	Energy Efficiency
EETVC	Energy Efficient Torque Vectoring Control
EM	Electric Motor
EV	Electric Vehicle
FRM	Fast Running Models
FRP	Fiber Reinforced Polymeric
FWD	Front Wheel Drive
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
HV	High Voltage
HW	Hardware
ICR	Instantaneous Centre of Rotation
IL	Imitation Learning
IMPC	Intelligent Model Predictive Control
IP	Intellectual Property
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
KPI	Key Performance Improvements
LUT	Look-Up Table
MaaS	Mobility-as-a-Service
ML	Machine Learning
MPC	Model Predictive Control

NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NNMPC	Neural Network-based Model Predictive Control
OBCA	Optimization-Based Control Allocation
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
POD	Platform on demand
PSB	Project Steering Board
R&D	Research and Development
RBCA	Rule-Based Control Allocation
RWD	Rear Wheel Drive
SCS	SmartCorners System
SDA	System Domain Analysis
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SUV	Sport Utility Vehicle
SW	Software
TVC	Torque Vectoring Control
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WP	Work Package

11 Sources

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